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The kinetics of the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol

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IT is well known that the first two members of the homologous series of dicarboxylic acids, malonic and oxalic acids, readily undergo decarboxylation in many solvents. Fraenkel et al¹ established the mechanism of decarboxylation of both the acids on the basis of their kinetic studies. The author studied the decarboxylation of malonic² and oxalic³ acids in resorcinol and catechol in his earlier investigations. Clark studied the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in aniline, *o*-Toluidine⁴ and in several ethers⁵, reporting that oxanilic acid decomposes by the same mechanism as followed by malonic and oxalic acids. Since oxanilic acid is a mono-derivative of oxalic acid, it was of interest to study the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol, in order to ascertain whether or not it follows the same mechanism as followed by oxalic and malonic acids.

Experimental :

Materials :

Oxanilic acid used was of E Merck (Darmstadt). m.p. = 150° stored over chemically pure magnesium perchlorate. Resorcinol and catechol used were BDH analytical reagents. No further purification of these chemicals was done.

Apparatus and Technique :

The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant temperature oil-bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by measuring the volume of carbon dioxide gas evolved at constant pressure. The apparatus and technique are the same as described in our previous articles⁶⁻⁷. A weighed amount of oxanilic acid (0.2-0.3g) was taken and dropped in the molten solvent (50g resorcinol), and in another set of 50g catechol. The carbon dioxide gas was collected at room temperature in the gas burette filled with water previously saturated with carbon dioxide. Duplicate experimental runs were

made and the deviation in the results was within $\pm 1.32\%$ in resorcinol and $\pm 1.55\%$ in catechol.

TABLE 1. APPARENT FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF OXANILIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

Temperature °C	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹ .	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ Sec ⁻¹
	Resorcinol	Catechol
140	6.91	7.01
150	11.48	11.48
155	19.50	17.78
160	32.36	26.92
165	53.70	31.62
170	91.20	63.10

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

	Resorcinol		Catechol	
	Oxanilic acid	Oxalic ^a acid	Oxanilic acid	Oxalic ^a acid
Log A, (Sec ⁻¹)	16.46	12.66	12.82	9.50
E _a , kcal mole ⁻¹	37.58	28.99	30.58	23.80
ΔF [‡] , kcal mole ⁻¹	30.62	31.39	30.81	31.21
ΔS [‡] , cal. mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	16.06	-5.85	-0.58	-17.93
ΔH [‡] , kcal. mole ⁻¹	36.72	28.07	29.72	22.89

^a Reference 3.

Results and Discussion :

The rate of decarboxylation of oxanilic acid was measured in resorcinol and catechol at six temperatures in the range 140°-170°. The plot of $\log (V_\infty - V_t)$ vs t was linear in almost all the experiments indicating that the reaction is first order, where V_∞ is the volume of carbon dioxide after completion of the reaction and V_t is the volume at any time t . The average rate constants calculated from the slopes of the experimental logarithmic plots are shown in Table 1. The rate of decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol at 140° and 150° is the same. Above 150° faster rates have been observed in resorcinol than in catechol. The decarboxylation rates of malonic, oxalic, benzoic, and substituted benzoic acids are lower in catechol than in resorcinol at all temperatures. Due to this abnormal behaviour several experimental runs were made and the results were quite reproducible.

The lower rates at 140°-150° indicate that at these temperatures only one hydroxyl group of catechol forms the hydrogen bonding with the carbonyl group of the oxanilic acid. Above 150° the other carbonyl group of the oxanilic acid associates with the other hydroxyl group of the catechol, and a bulkier intermediate complex causes the slow decomposition. It has been reported that the decarboxylation is faster in acidic than in basic medium. In the present study, even if catechol is more acidic than resorcinol, it is found that this general rule is not obeyed. However, the slow rates for the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in catechol are due to an intermediate com-

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plex formed through hydrogen bonding, the complex being more stable in catechol than in resorcinol. This is in agreement with the previous work.

The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Eyring equation from the data of Table 1, and are shown in Table 2. The energy of activation for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid in resorcinol is higher than in catechol, and it appears that the reaction mechanism in these solvents is identical. The entropy of activation is much more positive in resorcinol than in catechol, which indicates that the complex is more stable in catechol and the association is weaker in resorcinol. The thermodynamic parameters for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid falls in the same line (Table 2, columns 2 and 4). The high values of enthalpy of activation also indicate that a weaker attraction exists between the solute and solvent for the decarboxylation of oxalic acid in resorcinol. The structures of the complexes can be written as

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Electronic Property of Photosensitive Film Formation on Silver in Aqueous Solution of Hydrogen Sulphide

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SILVER reacts extremely slowly with aqueous hydrogen sulphide solution in free access to oxygen giving a greyish black film of Ag_2S . The film exhibits all the chemical properties of Ag_2S . In the present work the electronic property of the film has been studied.

Experimental :

Silver specimen of composition 99.8% Ag was used. It was cleaned and polished according to the method suggested by Champion². The cleaned silver coupon was immersed in saturated aqueous solution of hydrogen sulphide. The two surfaces of the treated silver plate were connected to a ballistic galvanometer, one surface was exposed to sunlight and the other was kept in the dark. The photocurrent produced was noted with time interval of exposure in seconds. The intensity of light at the exposed surface was 22500 lumens. The size of the silver specimen was 3×3 cms (22 S.W.G.).

Fig. 1.

Discussion :

Rohde and Hermann³ have studied the photoelectric effects of silver sulphide single crystals. Silver sulphide is sensitive to luminous or U.V. radiations. K. Friedrich and A. Leroux⁴ have found that argentite is decomposed by exposure to sunlight. The surface becomes covered with a fine dust when exposed to intense solar light.